

ADVANCED EXPERIENCES OF MODERN ENLIGHTENERS AS A STRATEGY FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: In the article, the first journalistic articles of modern enlighteners in the official press, including children's education and attitude to reading, as well as the ideas put forward about the preservation of the purity of the Turkish language, an opinion about the dedication of cultural and educational enthusiasts such as Behbudi, Elbek, Ramzi held.

Key words: journalism, modernity, press, education, textbook, classic, tradition, research, patriot, spirituality, value, thinking, publisher, journalist.

The beginning of the 20th century of Uzbek history is consistently studied in the literary studies of the independence period as a separate history and research. In particular, large-scale monographs and textbooks covering various aspects of creative, political, journalistic, organizational, pedagogical and publishing activities of enlightened intellectuals have been created. At the same time, it is recognized that the school textbooks and press publications, which showed a special attitude of the country's intellectuals to childhood, became a reality at the beginning of the last century.

It was not for nothing that the Jadids paid more attention to children in order to achieve national liberation, political independence, and improve the material and spiritual life of the people. The need to open new schools was also the need to realize that it is not just the delivery of employees sitting in the store and typing. Organizers of these schools were creators and pedagogues such as Saidrasul Azizi, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abduqadir Shakuri, Siddiqi-Azzi, Munavvarqori, Abdulla Avloni, Muhammadsharif Sofizoda, Abdurauf Fitrat, Sadriddin Ainiy. They created many books for the students of the school they opened, such as "Teacher first" (Saidrasul Azizi), "Adibi first" (Munavvarqari), "First teacher" (Abdulla Avloni), "Tahsib us-sibyon" (Sadriddin Ainiy). They compiled and published educational manuals on the alphabet and textbooks, mother tongue and literature, spelling rules, geography, accounting. In addition, they organized "community charities" for the purpose of creating conditions for poor children to get an education, sending talented young people abroad for training.

The first quarter of the 20th century is remembered as a terrible memory because of the drying of the pillow of the country's intellectuals, writers and creators. But important changes were made in Turkestan even during such conflicts, open and secret massacres. One of such historical realities is the new serious responsibility of adults for children and new schools' textbooks and study guides, the second one was the press of the people in the national language.

Mahmudhoja Behbudi is one of such blessed figures who is at the head of the enlightenment movement, concerned about the future of children and adolescents. The writer, who got acquainted with European-style schools and educational institutions in countries such as Arabia, Turkey, and Egypt, in addition to implementing what he saw and learned in the field of education in the country, wrote his opinions in "Bukhara method is modern", "Address to youth", " His efforts to reach the public through many journalistic articles such as "Travel Memories" are particularly noteworthy. The publicist's article "Islahi Tahsil" reflects the life of schools and madrasas. In it, the illiteracy of children is shown on the basis of evidence: the author is angry that a child who has studied in the same class for ten years and has barely mastered the alphabet is called a mullah. For this reason, he notes that it is a pity that "he could not read and extract the meaning if he put a Persian or Turkish book in front of him, or letters from the treasury and commercial office." The writer rightly objects to the fact that school teachers simply teach the works of Bedil, Khoja Hafiz, Navoi, Fuzuli, Sa'di and "Chahor Kitab" to the students: it is not due to the lack of education of the school teachers that only the pronunciation is analyzed and the content is not explained. ate.

Behbudi, who wrote about such urgent problems, laments that the main reason for the ignorance of teachers and teachers, lack of love for children and lack of consequences is the loss of the local people. In particular, it is worth noting that the life of Turkestan students is compared with the knowledge and living standards of children of other nations: our children are looking for work from door to door with dirty and torn clothes and bare feet. Let's look carefully at the cities, how many of our property, trade and profession have been transferred to others since the 25th. "What will happen after 25 days? Moziy is the scale of perspective, let everyone measure it and know."

Every nation in the world has a period of development and at the same time a period of political and economic decline. Mahmudhoja Behbudi lived in a time when our country was in economic, spiritual, and political decline. As a

conscious child of the nation, he was not indifferent to the fate of the country and his compatriots. That is why he set an example in many areas as the leader of the Jadidist movement. Elbek (Mashriq Yunusov) focused all his attention on the future of the nation. His main goal is to improve the moral education of young people, to develop their consciousness and thinking, and in a number of journalistic articles of the writer, serious problems in the field of education are raised, the reasons for the lack of interest in medicine teachers and educational institutions, the lack of talented national personnel are analyzed, the tasks of modern youth and tasks are defined.

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